

D3.1 OS Landscape analysis and potential engagement targets

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Abbreviations and Acronyms

ASEAN	Association of Southeast Asian Nations
AOSP	African Open Science Platform
CoP	Communities of Practice
EC	European Commission
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
ESFRI	European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
GORC	Global Open Research Commons
GOSC	Global Open Science Cloud
HEIs	Higher Education Institutions
KERs	Key Exploitable Results
NRENs	National Research and Education Networks
IG	Interest Group
RDA	Research Data Alliance
SDG	United Nations Sustainable Development Goal
SRIA	Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda
TAB	RDA Technical Advisory Board
TG	Task Group
UNESCO	United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization
WG	Working Group

Executive summary

RDA TIGER establishes a suite of concrete services to support the development of relevant and well-focused Working Groups of the Research Data Alliance (RDA). One element of RDA TIGER is the Landscape Analysis Service (WP3) which provides potential WGs and the Facilitation Service (WP5) with background knowledge of Open Science activities in related areas, with the rationale that no WG should duplicate existing work, and that landscape gaps and emerging challenges should be addressed.

The Landscape Analysis Service will contribute to those aims by building a knowledge base of selected resources. This deliverable sets out a description of the scope of the service, how the knowledge base will be built and the methodology behind identifying relevant initiatives to include at this early stage of the project.

The WP3 group engaged with this deliverable recognised early on the rapidly-changing nature and vast scope of the research data sharing landscape. Therefore this deliverable presents the first stage in establishing the Landscape Analysis Service. A further iteration of this deliverable is due in Month 18 (D3.4).

This deliverable is intended primarily for internal use and, in particular, to guide the Facilitation Service in their work to identify commonalities and complementarities.

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1. Introduction: aim(s) and scope of the landscape analysis task

1.1. Problem statement and scope

The Research Data Alliance's (RDA) Working Groups (WGs) aim to solve a specific research data related issue in a relatively short period of time¹. In practice, these groups are created by the RDA community: they rely on the community for communications activities in order to attract and gather participants, and they depend on the RDA Technical Advisory Board (TAB) to review the scope and relevance of their mission. While these processes have been demonstrated to be successful in the decade of RDA activities, certain areas have been identified where improvements can be made. As the research data landscape evolves, the number of actors and activities have increased tremendously. Additionally, the success of RDA activities has created a number of Working and Interest Groups (IGs), as well as RDA Recommendations and other Outputs, sometimes with very complex definitions and multiple potential use cases.

For a new WG (and even for the TAB members), it can be difficult to define:

- a) what has been previously done on a given subject and what should be considered in the Case Statements;
- b) who is already working on this subject area in the global Open Science (OS) landscape, including e.g., European Open Science Cloud projects, and;
- c) who has the necessary expertise and interest to participate in these actions.

The aim of the RDA TIGER Landscape Service is to collect information on the overall Open Science landscape which can support the RDA Working Groups supported by RDA TIGER to fulfil their mission.

Particularly important data sources for this purpose are the groups and outputs from the RDA and partner organisations, as well as other relevant (e.g., EOSC-related) projects. By doing this, the Landscape Service will help the WGs identify relevant activities in the field, target their recruitment and engagement actions accordingly, and communicate their results to the correct target audiences. To ensure a successful Landscape Service, it is essential that a body of knowledge is established for identifying and mapping international Open Science initiatives and infrastructures.

The RDA TIGER Landscape Service will create a seamless integration with other services provided by RDA TIGER. It supports the RDA TIGER Facilitation Services² particularly with planning and taking into account existing outputs, and by starting the WG with suitable members. It helps the Communications Service by identifying target audiences and helpful communications methods, while also supporting Output Services on defining the connections of the WG outputs.

The RDA TIGER Landscape Service includes two major parts: the development and maintenance of the landscape analysis database, and the provision of the actual landscape analyses to the WGs. The present

¹ The planned life of a WG is 18 months. Some WGs continue in 'maintenance mode' beyond that timeframe.

² <https://www.rd-alliance.org/rda-tiger> (accessed: 29.6.2023)

deliverable concentrates on the development processes and requirements for the landscape analysis database, and scopes the initial content of the database. It is important to understand that RDA TIGER is a part of the larger Open Science project environment, and the landscape analysis provided concentrates on what the project perceives to be immediate relevance to upcoming RDA WGs, a perception which will evolve during the project lifetime. Consequently, this deliverable provides the initial conception of the database and should not be considered a final or even complete picture of the Open Science landscape for this or any other purposes.

The RDA TIGER team to date has identified and gathered a range of community-endorsed initiatives via its network of trusted sources (RDA, CODATA). The aim of this is that the initiatives can be tagged and identified so they can be easily findable within the RDA TIGER Landscape Analysis Service and the RDA Maintenance Facility. The Maintenance Facility will enable all these resources to be referenced and tagged extensively with controlled vocabularies and ontologies using linked open data principles. If the outputs of RDA TIGER and the RDA WGs are properly tagged, they can be more discoverable and re-usable.

1.2. Landscape analysis database process and this deliverable

The overall structure of the landscape work can be defined as an iterative process (see Figure 1).

Figure 1. Landscape analysis database creation process. This deliverable describes the parts marked in blue.

The initial steps of the work are to define what the database is for and what it should contain. These considerations are combined in section 2.1 below with the identification process for key data sources, for example the RDA Working Groups and Interest Groups, the CODATA groups, and projects related to the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) for the landscape database (further explored in detail in section 3). Section 2.2 covers the description of the developed technical platform, which is very flexible and partly defines what kinds of data can be ingested and how they can be used. Lastly, this deliverable discusses the prioritisation of the data ingestion processes.

Going forward, WP3 will concentrate on data ingestion of the selected data sources (according to the prioritisation); provision of the landscape service to the RDA TIGER user communities; inclusion of other data ingestion processes (e.g., via opening the database interaction to outside projects and volunteers); and re-aligning the processes and data sources based on users, facilitation service providers or other relevant parties.

2. Approaches and methodologies considered

The initial approaches and methodologies considered for the landscape analysis activity were pragmatic options to deliver a usable service in an economical and resource-efficient way, whilst retaining sufficient flexibility to respond to the feedback that we will receive from both colleagues in the project team and from the RDA Working Group ‘service users’, as the active facilitation phase of the project commences.

In practical terms, there are two main aspects to the initial landscape analysis task. Firstly, there is the intellectual work — specifically the different ways of conceptualising the notion of ‘an Open Science landscape’ — and secondly, there are different ways to approach the technical format and delivery of the outputs of the knowledge work. The following section categorises the thinking behind these phases, and the overall structure for the landscape analysis service.

2.1 Initial landscape conceptualisations

The WP3 team began by considering differing high-level approaches to conceptualising an Open Science landscape. We initially saw the conceptual work developing through the following phases.

- Phase 1:
 - 1a) Identifying existing landscape analysis efforts
 - 1b) Ways of conceptualising the domain-agnostic landscape
 - 1c) Ways of conceptualising the domain-specific landscape
- Phase 2:
 - Geographical approaches.

2.1.1 Existing landscape analysis efforts

Phase 1 began with a meta-task: we were interested in collecting a preliminary list of contemporary efforts to carry out similar landscape analysis tasks and then identifying which of these other landscape analyses would be of value as reference documents. The overall aim is to collect a corpus of existing analyses to be investigated for inclusion in the RDA TIGER landscape analysis service.

The references that have been gathered to date are primarily those published in English, but relevant materials in languages in which WP members are fluent (including Dutch, Finnish, French, German, Greek, Scots, Spanish, and Swedish) will also be included. Keywords will be applied in English to allow all resources (whatever the original language) to be found alongside related items in the database.

The search strategy employed was first to gather the landscape reports to which we (Work Package members), or consortium colleagues, had contributed. Searching further, we consulted the extensive websites of RDA TIGER project partners RDA, CODATA, DANS and the Netherlands eScience Center. The next step was to conduct a search for relevant terms on wider collections of open research outputs, such as Zenodo³. The search was not concerned with every item relating to Open Science, open research data or FAIR research data; our focus was on landscape analyses, landscape reports and landscape reviews. One of the pernicious aspects of this particular activity is the speed with which such landscape efforts go out of date. We agreed that we would seriously consider relevant publications from the current and previous year only, that is to say 2023 and 2022, whilst noting older efforts as we found them relevant. The landscape reports discovered so far are set out in section 3, 'European and global Open Science initiatives identified and described'.

2.1.2 Ways of conceptualising the landscape

Having drawn together a useful preliminary list of landscape analysis reports, and having applied topic-related keywords to each for easy retrieval, the next step was to move on from this meta-task and to explore different ways of describing current practice in open research and open data. It was important to find sensible ways of categorising initiatives and organisations currently active in open research data within and beyond Europe, bearing in mind that new RDA WG proposals are likely to be concerned with i) a domain-agnostic tool, approach or issue; ii) a domain-specific data issue; iii) the application of (i) to (ii); and / or any of the above within specific geographical bounds.

With that in mind, one approach is to survey the landscape in a domain-agnostic way, in order to locate the projects and initiatives that are working on cross-cutting technical and policy issues relevant to multiple domains, and then subsequently to use domain-specific foci to capture further open data activity related to those domains. Finally, any open science or research data activity specific to or focused upon a nation, region or other geographical area was included in our survey. We noted each of

³ <https://zenodo.org/>

these categories using a simple multi-page Microsoft Excel workbook with separate spreadsheets for different conceptualisations of the landscape of contemporary Open Science activity.

Our initial organising schemata are as follows, and again each is unpacked in more detail in section 3, 'European and global Open Science initiatives identified and described'.

Ways of conceptualising the landscape (domain-agnostic):

- RDA Working Groups (with domain-agnostic focus);
- RDA Task Groups (with domain-agnostic focus);
- RDA Plenary Pathways (remaining aware that these have historically changed from plenary to plenary);
- European Open Science Cloud (EOSC)-funded projects (with domain-agnostic focus);
- EOSC Association coordinated Task Forces (with domain-agnostic focus);
- CODATA Task Groups (with domain-agnostic focus);
- CODATA Working Groups (with domain-agnostic focus);
- RDA Working Groups (with domain-agnostic focus);
- Global Open Science Cloud (GOSC) initiative Working Groups;
- WorldFAIR Project domain-agnostic activities;
- Global Open Research Commons (GORC) typology of elements;
- Research Software Alliance Task Forces⁴.

Ways of conceptualising the landscape (domain-specific):

- RDA Working Groups (with domain-specific focus);
- CODATA Task Groups (with domain-specific focus);
- CODATA Working Groups (with domain-specific focus);
- Global Open Science Cloud (GOSC) initiative Case Studies;
- WorldFAIR Project Case Studies;
- EOSC-funded projects (with domain-specific focus).

Ways of conceptualising the landscape (national approaches)

- RDA National groups: <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/national-groups>;
- CODATA National Committees: <https://codata.org/membership/national-members/>;
- Research Software Engineers national/multinational associations;
- Potentially the EOSC Observatory (currently under development): <https://eosc-portal.eu/news-and-events/news/introducing-eosc-observatory>.

It is clear from these initial investigations that the various views of the landscape outlined here offer potential value to the WG facilitation team. It will be important, both for the initial positioning inquiries we may receive and also for the purposes of making updates to Working Groups that are receiving

⁴ <https://www.researchsoft.org/taskforces/> (accessed: 29.6.2023)

facilitation support, that this set of categorisations is stored in such a way that the team can easily update and retrieve information throughout the lifespan of the RDA TIGER project.

Another important aspect for usability of the landscape information resource is its searchability — specifically the ability to quickly locate any projects or initiatives that are relevant to a given topic such as a particular technology, data issue or research area. To lay the foundation for a rich and searchable resource, we are preparing a set of keywords for each listed project or initiative based upon the descriptive text available. The database that will be populated with our landscape information will allow the user to search the titles, descriptions and keywords of each listed initiative, to allow effective location of all initiatives related to the search term(s).

2.2 Initial database design

2.2.1 Design considerations

The following design considerations apply for a database to support the landscape analysis, and future work linked to and associated with the landscape analysis:

1. **Flexibility:** the landscape analysis results, and any knowledge extraction and organisation resulting from it, needs to be flexible enough to allow a mixture of formal and informal classification, tagging, and contextualisation. The need is driven by three generic use cases:
 - a. RDA itself, which wants to be in a position to classify resources and knowledge elements fairly formally in respect of its own vocabularies and semantics;
 - b. The broader community, which will in principle benefit from the ability to link RDA-related resources and knowledge elements to a broader set of semantics, typically present in Scientific Knowledge Graphs and widely used in the landscape; and
 - c. Individual end users in specific communities, who may want to link and annotate resources formally to their specific semantics, or informally to reflect individual assessments of the resources or knowledge elements.
2. **Practical application:** We have, to date, identified some specific applications of the type of data envisaged for the landscape analysis result, and these are presented in Appendix B.
3. **Machine- and Human-readable:** the outputs and efforts resulting from the landscape analysis should ideally be maximally machine-readable, in addition to being human-readable.
4. **Re-use of infrastructure:** The RDA Maintenance Facility Project and a follow-up action in RDA TIGER (WP4) will create and operationalise a platform for the management, classification, and publication of RDA outputs, resources, and supplementary materials. This infrastructure is based on a graph database that contains at least minimum applicable metadata for each type of resource, but can already be extended and supplemented by formal and informal ‘tagging’ of resources. There is significant benefit to be gained if the landscape analysis outputs and results can be linked to this infrastructure, including:
 - a. Re-use and inheritance of relations that already exist in the graph database;
 - b. No need to duplicate any infrastructure;

- c. Ability to leverage the vocabularies, tag lists, and registry sources already identified and operationally available in the RDA Maintenance Facility.
- d. Re-use of machine and human interfaces wherever possible.

2.2.2 Options for implementation

The following broad alternatives are available for publication and dissemination of the landscape analysis:

1. **Publication of a narrative report:** Such a report serves as a definitive digital object that can be cited and is persistently available, but is not machine-actionable in any meaningful way.
2. **Using existing scholarly annotation platforms:** The ORKG⁵ and hypothes.is⁶ are examples of existing platforms that can be used to annotate and classify web resources both formally and informally. In both instances, one is not completely assured of the sustainability of these platforms, and as a long-term solution, it may not be completely satisfactory.
3. **The RDA Maintenance Facility:** This is designed to store, link, and annotate RDA outputs, resources and supplementary materials using RDA-defined vocabularies and tag lists⁷. There are no practical reasons why knowledge elements and nodes defining the RDA understanding of the landscape cannot be accommodated in the same graph. The longer-term sustainability is no more certain than the options in (2), but it is under RDA control.
4. **Hybrid solution:** We consider a hybrid solution, as described below, as a feasible and flexible option that satisfies the design considerations.

2.2.3 Hybrid solution

A hybrid solution will have the following components and features:

1. Landscape ontology: The RDA TIGER WG will identify foundational vocabularies and classification trees that adequately describe the landscape (an emerging list of these overlaps with the vocabularies, tag lists and registry references identified for the RDA Maintenance Facility). There is also an overlap with the Global Open Research Commons (GORC) Essential Elements of a research common currently published as Typology and Definitions⁸. These will be incorporated into the landscaping overview, as mentioned below in section 3.
2. The vocabularies used can be configured as an annotation form for referencing and linking information identified in any web-based resource — in essence the typical bibliographic

⁵ <https://orkg.org/> (accessed: 29.6.2023)

⁶ <https://web.hypothes.is/> (accessed: 29.6.2023)

⁷ RDA Maintenance Facility Vocabularies and Lists,
<https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1NWXsxfC8Oq99Po1E2NollyTGe-4lGOcW1LiFljncM/edit#gid=1069203209&range=A1>

⁸ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/group/global-open-research-commons-ig/outcomes/gorc-ig-typology-and-definitions> (accessed: 30.5.2023)

references that will form part of a narrative report. Such an annotation is stored in a graph database with the appropriate vocabulary and tag links, which means that

- a. the annotation itself and the wider set of connections are machine readable, and
 - b. a reference can be linked to multiple vocabulary elements or tags, and hence can support, assert, elaborate, or contextualise more than one concept in the landscape.
3. A narrative report is still useful and required — mostly for non-machine purposes — but using annotation of e.g., recommendations, guidelines, or best practices in the narrative report, one can also link the report to concepts in the landscape, which will by default also link these report elements to supporting references that have been annotated with the same concept elements.

The RDA Maintenance Facility will only become operational in the second half of 2023, and that will initially not be available to support the landscape analysis effort in RDA TIGER. It is, however, possible and feasible to use tools such as *hypothes.is* in the interim to annotate web references and resources with vocabulary elements and tags. Converting these annotations to a format that can be imported into the RDA Maintenance Facility Graph later on should not present any technical difficulties.

2.2.4 Conceptual data model

The conceptual data model is work in progress but is already broadly representative of the concepts, things, and relations that are needed to properly describe and contextualise the landscape.

The conceptual model allows linking any number of curated tag lists (for example the GORC Elements, Features, and Attributes of Data Infrastructure, or EOSC terminology) to the outputs, structures, and vocabulary in use by RDA. On this basis, we will be able to link elements of the landscape analysis to any or all of these concepts and entities as required. Appendix A provides more detail on this topic.

3.1 Existing landscape analyses as a data source

As discussed above in section 2.1, ‘Approaches and methodologies considered’, we began by looking for recent landscape reviews dealing with contemporary initiatives in research data policy and practice including FAIR and open data-related activities. Our initial findings were as follows (and this list will be added to as the project progresses):

Recent (i.e., 2022 and 2023) analyses:

- EC-commissioned ‘European Research Data Landscape’ (2022)⁹ event recording¹⁰: We note that this report examines the European research data landscape, and specifically attempts to characterise the progress made, and lacking, in the journey towards FAIR data. It does not attempt to provide an overview of Open Science or open data initiatives or organisations.
- FAIR-IMPACT ‘An overview of FAIR4RS and existing tools to assess FAIRness of software’ (2023)¹¹: An overview of the FAIR Principles for Research Software (FAIR4RS) and of the current landscape of FAIR metrics with a particular emphasis on metrics for software.
- EOSC Focus survey of current EOSC-related initiatives (at an early stage, at the time of writing).

For background, pre-2022 analyses:

- EOSC Executive Board Landscape Working Group, Landscape of EOSC-related infrastructures and initiatives, v2 (2020)¹²
- EOSC-Pillar overview of the EOSC Executive Board Landscape Working Group Landscape Analysis and Landscape Report (2020)¹³
- African Open Science Platform (2019) landscape study¹⁴
- FAIRsFAIR project, data policy landscape analysis, v1 (2019)¹⁵
- SSHOC project: ‘Exploring the SSH data landscape: thematic discovery portals in the EOSC’ (2020)¹⁶

The search for recent views of the Open Science and open data landscape has flagged a useful set of background resources for the reference of project members in readiness for the receipt of landscape inquiries as the WG facilitation service progresses (albeit a set that would benefit from further geographical coverage beyond Europe). However, it became clear that in order to thoroughly digest and

⁹<https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/03b5562d-6a35-11ed-b14f-01aa75ed71a1/language-en> (accessed: 30.5.2023)

¹⁰<https://symposium22.eoscfuture.eu/symposium/european-research-data-landscape-2021-2022-livestreamed/> (accessed: 30.5.23)

¹¹ <https://zenodo.org/record/7805608#.ZGSuCRZBxhE> (accessed: 30.5.2023)

¹²<https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/9c7f3c1e-2aea-11eb-9d7e-01aa75ed71a1/language-en/format-PDF/source-173604556> (accessed: 30.5.2023)

¹³ <https://www.eosc-pillar.eu/news/landscape-eosc-related-infrastructures-initiatives> (accessed: 30.5.2023)

¹⁴ https://aosplandata.org/wp-content/uploads/2022/05/aosplandscape-12aug2019_compressed.pdf (accessed 30.5.2023)

¹⁵ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5537032> (accessed: 30.5.2023)

¹⁶ <https://zenodo.org/record/4290599#.ZGSvphZBxhE> (accessed: 30.5.2023)

understand the existing recent efforts in landscape analysis work, to map coverage and identify gaps in areas of research or geographic area, this activity would need significant and sustained focus, and would risk drawing our attention from the stated practical scope of the task as described in section 1. On that basis, we propose to proceed with this concise list of landscape reviews and hope to expand this section and our analysis of it during the project lifetime.

As described above in section 2.1.2, ‘Ways of conceptualising the landscape’, we approached then moved forward with landscape categorisation using broad categories in a pragmatic way that will be useful to the RDA TIGER Facilitation Service activity, in the task of providing updates on the landscape as well as that of facilitating users in their discovery activities. These broad categories (specifically, domain-agnostic, domain-specific and geographical approaches) are described below: each section sets out the principal areas of activity of which the Landscape Analysis Service should be aware.

3.2 Ways of conceptualising the landscape (domain-agnostic)

3.2.1 RDA groups

The Open Science landscape is a rapidly moving field and the themes around its implementation develop each year. The RDA landscape of activities could be seen as a microcosm of this landscape. For clarity, we have broken down current RDA activities into existing WGs, IGs, Communities of Practice (CoPs) and National Groups. We have added two other categories of analysis of relevant RDA-related entities: recommendations and outputs; and RDA Pathways. In section 3.2 we deal with domain-agnostic expressions of the RDA world, and in section 3.3 we present the domain-specific aspects. The geographical groups are included in section 3.4.

3.2.1.1 RDA Working Groups (WGs) (domain-agnostic)

RDA WGs have a specific function in that they work for a short period of time (12-18 months) to produce a concrete output or recommendation. There are 47 current RDA WGs and 30 of these are dealing with cross-domain Open Science issues. It is worth noting here that the source of knowledge for the most current up to date list of RDA WGs is via the RDA website¹⁷: we are mindful that this list may not always be up-to-date, but we use it as the best reference point available. Given the large number of WGs, it can be challenging to categorise the many topics encompassed. The RDA Maintenance Facility (see section 2.2) will be a support mechanism here. The twice-yearly RDA Plenaries also serve as a good barometer for new and ongoing topics and most recently the majority of the WG topic meetings held have been around the topic of FAIR and infrastructure implementation. WP3 offers a key source of support to RDA WGs wishing to set up and to cross-check for overlaps in focus.

¹⁷ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/working-groups> (accessed: 30.5.2023)

3.2.1.2 RDA Interest Groups (IGs) (domain-agnostic)

The RDA Interest Groups are also a relevant resource for any landscape analysis effort. They differ from the WGs in the sense they are more exploratory and have a longer life-span. More abundant in number, there are 65 IGs currently running, of which 42 are domain-agnostic. IGs provide the forum for discussing and prioritising themes, and as such are often a springboard for work to be carried out more concretely in future WGs. The IGs are listed on the RDA website¹⁸. In the context of the Landscaping Service, IGs are very relevant for those wanting to set up groups, and should be thoroughly researched by the Facilitation Service as a resource for identification of relevant Open Science activities.

3.2.2 RDA outputs and recommendations (domain-agnostic)

The number of endorsed and community-reviewed RDA outputs and recommendations resulting from RDA groups increases each year, with 54 domain-agnostic outputs at the time of writing. These are listed on the RDA website¹⁹ where it is possible to search by topic and discipline. These will all be included as part of the information gathered on the current Open Science landscape. Relevant RDA outputs need to be flagged to any future RDA WG. Monitoring of current WGs is advised for potential outputs. Therefore, the Landscape Analysis Service should also involve checking the activities of WGs by keyword when advising on a new WG.

3.2.3 RDA Pathways

The RDA Plenary Pathways have been prepared by the RDA TAB since 2019 as a way of helping plenary attendees to navigate the diverse range of groups meeting at each plenary. They represent a pragmatic approach to grouping the densely populated RDA ecosystem into a series of high-level topics. Beyond supporting the plenaries, the pathways are also a good reflection of activities in RDA, and reflect topical issues in the Open Science landscape. The most up-to-date list of pathways has been added to the landscape analysis list; this consists of eleven topics including an ‘other’ category. The number of themes has grown: there were eight pathways two years ago and six pathways four years ago. In the successive iterations of pathways, one can discern the development of the topic of FAIR over the years in its different implementation approaches and nuances. Data Infrastructures have also emerged more strongly as a theme. The RDA Landscape Analysis Service will track the pathways from each plenary and use them as a resource to categorise the themes on which the RDA groups are working.

3.2.4 The European Open Science Cloud

At a European level, the Open Science landscape is largely structured around EC-funded activities contributing to the creation of the EOSC. In 2018, a commitment was agreed among member states to proceed with the establishment of an open and trustworthy digital environment for Europe’s research

¹⁸ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/interest-groups> (accessed: 29.06.2023)

¹⁹ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/recommendations-and-outputs/catalogue> (accessed: 30.5.2023)

outputs²⁰ as well as aiming to support FAIR implementation. A roadmap for setting up EOSC was published in 2020²¹. Implementing EOSC at both a technical and policy level is complex and rapidly developing. To date, a substantial number of projects supported by the EC have been carried out to support the early phase of EOSC implementation. The landscape group of the EOSC secretariat produced a report in 2020 examining all the initiatives relating to the development of EOSC. The activities around EOSC have been multi-faceted and have involved setting up governance structures, initiating community-led working groups and setting up a partnership for future work programme funding. RDA is involved at a European level, complemented by the funding of RDA TIGER²² and involvement in EOSC Future²³. Many European member states have invested significantly in e-infrastructures or data intensive European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures²⁴ (ESFRIs) and the aim of EOSC is to federate all these research support mechanisms. Knowledge of EOSC activities and outcomes of projects and task forces is a valuable addition to the Landscape Analysis Service. The service should also pay close attention to the activities of European e-infrastructures that are interoperating closely with the EOSC (for example GEANT²⁵, OpenAIRE²⁶, EGI²⁷); ESFRI Research Infrastructures, Cluster projects²⁸, and thematic initiatives.

The Landscape Service will actively monitor developments and outputs from the EOSC landscape. RDA WGs will need to know of complementary or overlapping activities with EOSC when writing case statements. Similarly, any resulting RDA outputs should also be promoted where relevant in the EOSC environment via the EOSC Association²⁹, with which RDA TIGER has close connections including representation from EOSC Association on the RDA Selection Committee (see RDA TIGER D6.1)³⁰.

3.2.4.1 Current EOSC-funded projects

The EOSC Partnership was set up in June 2021 to support the governance, financing and implementation of EOSC as a tripartite partnership between the EC, member states and the EOSC Association. Eighteen projects have recently started under the Horizon Europe Infra-EOSC 2022 programme with a mission to align and work towards a common EOSC vision; some are domain-agnostic while others are tackle FAIR

²⁰ <https://data.consilium.europa.eu/doc/document/ST-9526-2016-INIT/en/pdf> (accessed: 30.5.2023)

²¹ European Commission, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation. Jones, S., Abramatic, J., 2019. European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) strategic implementation plan. <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/202370> (accessed: 30.5.2023)

²² <https://www.rd-alliance.org/rda-tiger> (accessed: 30.5.2023)

²³ <https://eoscfuture.eu/> (accessed: 30.5.2023)

²⁴ <https://www.esfri.eu> (accessed: 29.6.2023)

²⁵ <https://geant.org> (accessed: 29.6.2023)

²⁶ <https://www.openaire.eu> (accessed: 29.6.2023)

²⁷ <https://www.egi.eu> (accessed: 29.6.2023)

²⁸ <https://eosc-portal.eu/esfri-thematic-cluster-projects> (accessed: 30.5.2023)

²⁹ <https://eosc.eu> (accessed: 29.6.2023)

³⁰ D6.1 Rules of Operation for the RDA TIGER Selection Committee <https://zenodo.org/record/8016331>

implementation in specific disciplines (e.g., AcquaInfra³¹, BY-COVID³², FAIR-EASE³³ amongst others). The projects will produce Key Exploitable Results (KERs) which are relevant to Open Science and data sharing both within and across disciplines. RDA TIGER will monitor the KERs and other outputs of the projects that have been funded under the Horizon Europe Infra-EOSC 2022 programme. Also important is to continue communication with EOSC Focus coordination efforts around the partnership³⁴.

3.2.4.2 EOSC SRIA

The EOSC Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA) defines the framework for future research, development and innovation in relation to the EOSC. It is of relevance to many of RDA's stakeholders such as Research Performing Organisations (RPOs), funders, service providers and non-governmental organisations (NGOs). The current version³⁵ of the SRIA was prepared in 2022, but is expected to evolve into future iterations in dialogue with the EOSC community. The following action areas have been identified in the SRIA as areas of activity needed to implement EOSC:

- Persistent Identifiers
- Metadata and ontologies
- FAIR metrics and certification
- Authentication and authorisation infrastructure - AAI
- User Environments
- EOSC Interoperability Framework
- Resource Provider Environments
- Rules of Participation
- Landscape monitoring
- Skills and training
- Rewards and recognition
- Widening to public and private sectors and going global.

This overview of activities provides useful categories which will be incorporated into the knowledge base of the Landscape Analysis Service.

3.2.4.3 EOSC Task Forces

A further area of activity which will need to be tracked by the landscape team is the group of EOSC Task Forces³⁶. There are currently thirteen EOSC TFs underway, under the following four domain-agnostic headings: Metadata; Research Careers; Technical Challenges; and Sustaining EOSC. Each Task Force has a charter and a planned output phase. We will maintain a regular channel of communication with the

³¹ <https://aquainfra.eu> (accessed: 29.06.2023)

³² <https://by-covid.org> (accessed: 29.06.2023)

³³ <https://www.fairease.eu/> (accessed 29.06.2023)

³⁴ <https://eosc.eu/eosc-focus-project> (accessed: 29.06.2023)

³⁵ <https://eosc.eu/sites/default/files/SRIA%201.1%20final.pdf> (accessed: 30.05.2023)

³⁶ <https://eosc.eu/eosc-task-forces> (accessed: 30.5.2023)

EOSC Association in order to ensure that any updates or outputs from the Task Forces are included in our monitoring.

3.2.5 CODATA Task Groups (domain-agnostic)

CODATA Task Groups (TGs) are groups of scientists, researchers and data experts who work together on a specific problem or theme to advance the state of data management. TGs are proposed according to a procedure defined by the CODATA Constitution, and they are approved and endorsed by the biennial CODATA General Assembly. The current cohort of TGs was approved in November 2021 and in most cases will run until October 2023 when they will either be closed or re-approved. Most of the TGs can be considered to have a focus on a given domain or research area and are therefore listed under domain-specific approaches, section 3.3.6 below, but of the current crop the following four groups can be considered as domain-agnostic efforts:

- Advanced mathematical tools for data-driven applied systems analysis³⁷
- CODATA-WDS TG on Data from Participatory Mapping for the SDGs and Knowledge³⁸
- Digital Representation of Units of Measurement (DRUM)³⁹
- Improving Data Access and Reusability (IDAR)⁴⁰

These Task Groups tackle a technical or policy aspect of data science or stewardship which is relevant across multiple research areas. Accordingly, those who are interested in initiating an RDA WG in a related area should be aware of these existing Task Groups, their progress, personnel and outputs.

3.2.6 CODATA Working Groups (domain-agnostic)

The CODATA Executive Committee may set up Working Groups to explore the need for CODATA action on specific issues, not normally for more than two years. For example, the Data Ethics Working Group⁴¹ was approved by the CODATA General Assembly in November 2021. Furthermore, several Working Groups are active under the CODATA Decadal Programme, including:

- Global Open Science Cloud (GOSC) Working Groups and Case Studies⁴² (see section 3.2.7 for a fuller discussion);
- IUSSP-CODATA WG on FAIR Vocabularies⁴³.

³⁷ <https://codata.org/initiatives/task-groups/applied-systems-analysis/> (accessed: 30.5.2023)

³⁸ <https://codata.org/initiatives/task-groups/citizen-science-for-the-sustainable-development-goals/> (accessed: 30.5.2023)

³⁹ <https://codata.org/initiatives/task-groups/drum/> (accessed: 30.5.2023)

⁴⁰ <https://codata.org/initiatives/task-groups/idar/> (accessed: 30.5.2023)

⁴¹ <https://codata.org/initiatives/working-groups/data-ethics/> (accessed: 30.5.2023)

⁴² <https://codata.org/initiatives/decadal-programme2/global-open-science-cloud/> (accessed: 30.5.2023)

⁴³ <https://codata.org/initiatives/decadal-programme2/fair-vocabularies/iussp-codata-working-group-on-fair-vocabularies/> (accessed: 30.5.2023)

Again, proposed RDA WGs on related areas of focus should be aware of the progress, personnel and outputs from these activities.

3.2.7 Global Open Science Cloud (GOSC)

The Global Open Science Cloud initiative⁴⁴ aims to encourage cooperation, alignment and ultimately interoperability among a number of open science cloud or commons initiatives. One of the distinctive features of the GOSC initiative is its methodology comprising thematic Working Groups and a set of domain or cross-domain case studies. The Working Groups address a set of issues shared across Open Science infrastructures, including: governance and sustainability; policy and legal issues; alignment of technical infrastructure; and data and metadata interoperability. Please note that the GOSC also runs a crop of domain-specific and cross-domain case studies, discussed in section 3.3.9 below.

3.2.8 WorldFAIR project cross-domain activities

The WorldFAIR project⁴⁵ aims to improve data interoperability across domains and multidomain research areas. The project leverages 11 case studies to demonstrate how different disciplines can align on data challenges such as FAIR data, data management and stewardship and the co-design of interoperability workflows. The case studies have a broad international distribution and serve as a unique way of identifying how disciplines can work together and work on the internationalisation of principles, and across disciplinary boundaries and how to make the data more usable. The case studies, each of which are focused upon a specific domain or cross-domain research area, are listed in section 3.3.8 below. In close collaboration with the WorldFAIR team, we will ensure the outputs of the case studies are fed into the landscape analysis and are appropriately reflected in the categories used.

3.2.9 Global Open Research Commons (GORC) typology of elements

A seminal RDA activity has been the collaboration around the concept of an “Open Research Commons”. The work has stemmed from the RDA GORC WG⁴⁶. The definition of a commons is “*A global trusted ecosystem that provides seamless access to high quality interoperable research outputs and services*”.⁴⁷ As such commons are emerging in different regions of the world, it is crucial that these efforts align and learn from each other with the ultimate aim of making them interoperable, thus serving international data sharing. It may be the case that RDA’s community wishes to build tools to meet the needs of these commons. As part of the GORC landscape activities, the task has worked on collecting all the available models that are gathering attributes of the Open Science landscape, from a domain-agnostic perspective. To fully grasp the complexity of international Open Science initiatives, the GORC team has extensively analysed each typology and has generated a set of attributes that are part of commons development. A breakdown of the essential elements has been collated, and this reflects an effort to systematically identify a set of core functions and activities across international commons.

⁴⁴ <https://codata.org/initiatives/decadal-programme2/global-open-science-cloud/>; <https://www.goscloud.net/>

⁴⁵ <https://worldfair-project.eu/> (accessed: 30.5.2023)

⁴⁶ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/gorc-international-model-wg> (accessed: 30.5.2023)

⁴⁷ GORC IG: *Typology and Definitions*, DOI: [10.15497/RDA00087](https://doi.org/10.15497/RDA00087) (accessed: 30.5.2023)

Figure 3. The GORC typology⁴⁸

Figure 3 shows the three elements in blue as the underpinning digital elements that constitute the parts of the commons with which people interact. The five elements in white are the social/human elements that are needed to make the commons succeed. The central element in dark blue represents the positioning of standards at the core of this commons initiative. This typology will be added to the Maintenance Facility and provide a set of criteria against which the RDA TIGER Facilitation Service can regularly check for activities created under these categories.

3.2.10 Research Software Alliance Task Forces

The Research Software Alliance aims to “bring research software communities together to collaborate on the advancement of the research software ecosystem, to achieve the vision that research software and those who develop and maintain it are recognised and valued as fundamental and vital to research worldwide.”⁴⁹ To achieve these goals, the ReSA runs a number of Task Forces focused on particular domain-agnostic concerns that are of relevance to research software engineers. The current Task Forces are:

⁴⁸ Ibid. footnote 20.

⁴⁹ <https://www.researchsoft.org/taskforces/> (accessed: 29.6.2023)

- Code Availability;
- Database of Research Software Funding Opportunities;
- Research Institution Policies to Support Research Software.

Whilst the search for funding opportunities is universal, there are certain aspects of code availability and the development of policies to support research software which have clear implications for open science, FAIR data and FAIR software.

3.2.11 Advisory organisations

Consideration should be given to organisations that generate policy, position statements and recommendations applicable to multiple domains in the research data space, and whose work is likely to be relevant to those considering the establishment of a new RDA WG. Examples include bodies such as Knowledge Exchange⁵⁰, Science Europe⁵¹, the Digital Curation Centre⁵², and the Digital Preservation Coalition⁵³. The challenge is, of course, to identify which of a potentially extensive list of such organisations will be most likely to be useful for the purposes of our landscaping activity; an initial list will be added to the database and this list will be expanded during the project lifetime. GO FAIR⁵⁴ is an initiative that has also produced a number of domain agnostic materials to support FAIR implementation across implementation networks, as well as the development of more domain-specific support materials (see section 3.3.10 below).

3.3 Ways of conceptualising the landscape (domain-specific)

It is important also to survey the landscape of domain-specific activities.. Below is an overview of the priority areas in relation to which the Landscape Analysis Service will collect information and maintain awareness.

3.3.1 RDA Working Groups (domain-specific)

There are currently 17 domain-specific RDA WGs: they cover topics that range from Agriculture Sciences, Earth, Space and Environmental Science, Health Data, and Neuroimaging. There is often more than one WG working in relation to a given field. In 2020, nine COVID-19 WGs were established, largely to define data sharing practices for COVID-19 research. Overseen by an overarching COVID-19 WG, the initiative has four thematic areas associated with it (Clinical, Omics, Epidemiology and Social Sciences), as well as a further four domain-agnostic challenges (community participation, indigenous data, ethical, and research software) to support how they can be applied in the COVID-19 domain. RDA TIGER Landscape

⁵⁰ <https://knowledge-exchange.info/about-us> (accessed: 30.5.2023)

⁵¹ <https://www.scienceeurope.org> (accessed: 30.5.2023)

⁵² <https://dcc.ac.uk/> (accessed: 30.5.2023)

⁵³ <https://www.dpconline.org/> (accessed: 30.5.2023)

⁵⁴ <https://www.go-fair.org/> (accessed 21.6.2023)

Analysis Service will monitor the outputs of these domain-specific outputs in the event that new domain-specific WGs might build on the outputs.

3.3.2 RDA Interest Groups (domain-specific)

For RDA IGs, 23 out of 65 are domain-specific in focus (using the same methodology as for the domain-specific WGs in section 3.3.1). As IGs can run on for a longer period of time, they can be more exploratory in nature and one IG can also cover many sub-disciplines. Thirteen domains are represented among current IGs: Biodiversity⁵⁵, Chemistry, Economics, Ethnography, Environmental sciences, Geospatial, Global Water, Health, Life Sciences, Linguistics, Psychological, Photon and Neutron Science, and Social Sciences⁵⁶. RDA IGs are very active and tend to be exploratory in nature. While they don't need to produce concrete outputs (although some do), they can be a good reflection of the changing data sharing landscape.

3.3.3 RDA Communities of Practice

In an effort to build discipline- or domain-specific communities, the RDA introduced Communities of Practice (CoP) to its portfolio of groups in December 2020. CoPs investigate, discuss and provide knowledge and skills within a specific discipline and/or research domain. Composed of experts from that area, CoPs are committed to directly or indirectly enabling data sharing, exchange and/or interoperability by serving as *the* coordination focal point for RDA in those specific disciplines/research domains (RDA, 2021).

There is currently only one RDA CoP: the Improving Global Agricultural Data (IGAD) Community of Practice, which emerged from an earlier Interest Group and intensive set of activities in this area.

3.3.4 RDA outputs and recommendations (domain-specific)

It is possible to search discipline-specific RDA outputs via the RDA Outputs Catalogue⁵⁷. A search across the primary disciplines (according to the Frascati classification⁵⁸) displays 17 current domain-specific outputs. These mainly focus on health and COVID data, as well as domain-specific metadata applications.

⁵⁵ For example the Biodiversity Data Integration Group <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/biodiversity-data-integration-ig.html>

⁵⁶ It should be noted that RDA TIGER uses the words domains and discipline interchangeably. There are traditional disciplines but at the same time, many new cross-domain research areas are being established which are interdisciplinary research areas and domains.

⁵⁷ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/recommendations-and-outputs/catalogue> (accessed: 30.5.2023)

⁵⁸ <https://www.oecd.org/innovation/frascati-manual-2015-9789264239012-en.htm>, p. 59. (accessed: 30.5.2023)

In addition, RDA has developed a number of discipline-specific pages⁵⁹ that reflect the use of relevant practices and tools in a range of disciplines, particularly those that are not so well served by infrastructures and require data sharing tools. These resources may well be relevant to future WGs that want to start work in these areas.

RDA's work in EOSC Future will also release a set of domain-specific Information sheets for a range of disciplines getting started in Open Science. In addition, in the context of the EOSC Future project, RDA runs a programme of domain ambassadors⁶⁰ who will produce a range of potentially useful outputs, e.g. data sharing requirements. RDA TIGER should monitor the outcomes of the EOSC Future task in this area and keep abreast of the disciplinary communities in RDA for relevant domain-specific outputs.

3.3.5 CODATA Working Groups (domain-specific)

The CODATA Executive Committee sets up Working Groups to explore the need for CODATA action on specific issues, for not normally more than two years. The 'Creative Living and Aging through Cross-disciplinary Utilisation of Data' Working Group⁶¹ was approved by the CODATA General Assembly in November 2021. In 2023, the OneGeochemistry Working Group⁶² was established as a result of the WorldFAIR project⁶³.

3.3.6 CODATA Task Groups (domain-specific)

As explained in more detail in section 3.2.5, CODATA TGs are groups of experts from various backgrounds working on science and data management issues surrounding specific problems and themes. The following domain-specific TGs were approved or renewed at the 32nd CODATA General Assembly, held in November 2021⁶⁴:

- a) Agriculture Data, Knowledge for Learning and Innovation
- b) Applying Data Integration and Data Science Tools toward Research of Urban Life and Smart Cities
- c) Extension of InChI for Nanomaterials (New Task Group)
- d) FAIR Data for Disaster Risk Research (FAIR-DRR)
- e) Fundamental Physical Constants Task Group (recognised as a standing initiative of CODATA since 2016.)

⁵⁹ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/rda-disciplines> (accessed: 02.6.2023)

⁶⁰ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/rda-disciplines/rda-europe-ambassadors-2022> (accessed: 02.6.2023)

⁶¹ <https://codata.org/initiatives/working-groups/creative-living-and-aging-through-cross-disciplinary-utilization-of-data/> (accessed: 30.5.2023)

⁶² <https://codata.org/initiatives/decadal-programme2/worldfair/onegeochemistry-wg/> (accessed: 30.5.2023)

⁶³ <https://worldfair-project.eu/> (accessed: 02.6.2023)

⁶⁴ <https://codata.org/events/general-assembly/general-assembly-2021/> (accessed: 02.6.2023)

In this list of groups, a focus on a ‘domain’ also includes focus on a cross-domain or multi-domain research area. Examples here include Disaster Risk Research and Smart Cities research, each of which are an emerging cross-domain research area that incorporates the epistemologies and methods of several Frascati-defined research domains (OECD 2015, p. 59).

3.3.7 Current EOSC-funded projects (domain-specific)

Please see section 3.2.4.1 above, ‘Current EOSC-funded projects’, for a discussion of domain-specific activities funded by the EOSC and their relevance to RDA TIGER.

3.3.8 WorldFAIR case studies

The aim of the WorldFAIR project is to improve the interoperability of research data across domains and multidomain research areas. Thus, the project itself tackles the cross-cutting issue of data interoperability as is included in the overview of domain-agnostic initiatives (see section 3.2.8 above). However, the core of the WorldFAIR project are the 11 case studies, which represent a wide range of sciences, communities and challenges. Each of the case studies are listed below, as discrete domain-specific activities, listed with the countries where the case study’s partners are based:

- Chemistry (USA / international*)⁶⁵ ⁶⁶
- Nanomaterials (UK / Cyprus / Germany)⁶⁷
- Geochemistry (Australia / Germany / USA)⁶⁸
- Social surveys (Australia / Norway)⁶⁹
- Population health (UK / Tanzania / Kenya / international**)⁷⁰
- Urban health (USA / Latin America)⁷¹
- Biodiversity (Denmark / international**)⁷²
- Agricultural biodiversity (Brazil / Belgium / USA / Kenya)⁷³
- Ocean science and sustainable development (Germany / international****)⁷⁴
- Disaster risk reduction (New Zealand)⁷⁵
- Cultural heritage (Eire).⁷⁶

⁶⁵ https://worldfair-project.eu/case-studies-of-worldfair_trashed/chemistry-wp3/ (accessed: 30.5.2023)

⁶⁶ <https://iupac.org/worldfair-global-cooperation-on-fair-data-policy-and-practice/> (accessed: 30.5.2023)

⁶⁷ <https://worldfair-project.eu/nanomaterials/> (accessed: 30.5.2023)

⁶⁸ <https://worldfair-project.eu/geochemistry/> (accessed: 30.5.2023)

⁶⁹ <https://worldfair-project.eu/social-surveys/> (accessed: 30.5.2023)

⁷⁰ <https://worldfair-project.eu/population-health/> (accessed: 30.5.2023)

⁷¹ <https://worldfair-project.eu/urban-health/> (accessed: 30.5.2023)

⁷² <https://worldfair-project.eu/biodiversity/> (accessed: 30.5.2023)

⁷³ <https://worldfair-project.eu/agricultural-biodiversity/> (accessed: 30.5.2023)

⁷⁴ <https://worldfair-project.eu/ocean-science-sustainable-development/> (accessed: 30.5.2023)

⁷⁵ <https://worldfair-project.eu/disaster-risk-reduction/> (accessed: 30.5.2023)

⁷⁶ <https://worldfair-project.eu/cultural-heritage/> (accessed: 30.5.2023)

*International union (IUPAC).

**International organisation based in France (CODATA).

***Intergovernmental organisation based in Denmark (GBIF).

****United Nations organisation (UNESCO Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission).

This list demonstrates engagement with a diverse set of domains and cross-domain research areas by WorldFAIR case studies. These will be relevant to those interested in data issues arising from each research area, or data issues in each country, as well as any prospective WGs intending to tackle cross-domain data interoperability issues.

3.3.9 Global Open Science Cloud (GOSC) case studies

The GOSC is discussed in section 3.2.7 above. The Cloud project itself is domain-agnostic, and is developed and refined via domain-specific or cross-domain case studies. Domains and research areas include: Incoherent scatter radar data fusion and computation; Biodiversity and ecology information platform; SDG-13 climate change and natural disasters; Sensitive data federation analysis model in population health; and Open reproducible raw diffraction data for access in pandemics.

3.3.10 GO FAIR domain-specific networks

The GO FAIR network has developed some domain-specific materials that are worth adding to the landscape analysis; for example, support materials for FAIR implementation in the nanosafety domain, via the AdvancedNano⁷⁷ network. In addition GO FAIR has supported the creation of the Virus Outbreak Data Network (VODAN)⁷⁸ an initiative to support a FAIR approach to virus-related research data.

3.4 Ways of conceptualising the landscape (geographical approaches)

Another dimension of the research data landscape is geographical. Awareness of geographically bound initiatives and organisations will help those who may wish to either set up an RDA working group with a geographical focus, or who simply wish to know of relevant people in various geographical areas with whom to collaborate, to encourage a healthily diverse group of members. The main geographical divisions that we have used are a) national, and b) regional.

3.4.1 National approaches

This deliverable is not intended to present an infrastructure landscape overview of each country but the RDA TIGER team needs to be specifically aware of national activities in Open Science. Many national

⁷⁷ <https://www.go-fair.org/implementation-networks/overview/advancednano/> (accessed: 21.6.2023)

⁷⁸ <https://www.go-fair.org/implementation-networks/overview/vodan/> (accessed: 21.6.2023)

research environments, ministries and funding units, particularly in Europe, have been and are increasingly invested in Open Science and putting this on their national digital agendas. As a result, numerous infrastructures have been developed that provide infrastructural research support as well as policy and training support. It is beyond the scope of this deliverable to add all the national approaches here, and there are some existing landscaping efforts available⁷⁹. However, the RDA TIGER Landscape Analysis Service needs to be aware and where possible leverage its international network and keep abreast of the topics national infrastructures are addressing. A concrete example is Germany: the German national infrastructure is developing cross-cutting themes including ‘Metadata’, ‘Ethical, Legal and Social Matters’, ‘Common Infrastructures’, ‘Training and Education’, and ‘Industry Engagement’⁸⁰. These topics and subsequent working groups will produce outputs of relevance to future RDA groups.

3.4.1.1 RDA national nodes

RDA has national nodes in Australia, Brazil, Canada, Costa Rica, and the USA. These are listed here: <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/national-groups-0>.

There are also RDA Europe national nodes in 22 European countries, listed here: <https://rd-alliance.org/groups/rda-europe-national-nodes>

National approaches and activities in Open Science are important to landscaping. The landscape service team will monitor the RDA national nodes and also use other multiplier networks such as the OpenAIRE nodes⁸¹ to add any relevant outputs to the landscape.

3.4.1.2 CODATA National Committees

A National Member is a scientific academy, research council, scientific institution, or association of such institutions, which has activities in research data. Each National Member is expected to establish a national committee⁸² for maintaining liaison between its national activities and the CODATA secretariat (CODATA 2022). At the time of writing, CODATA has nineteen national committees representing the following countries: Austria, Australia, Botswana, Canada, China, Finland, India, Israel, Japan, Kenya, Korea, Mongolia, New Zealand, Russia, South Africa, Taiwan, Ukraine, United Kingdom, and the United States of America. National Committee members organise conferences and meetings, network with other colleagues and organisations based in their country to collaborate on research, data-related challenges, and contribute to international partnerships with other CODATA national committees. Those proposing an RDA working group that intends to focus on research data-related activity in one or more of these countries will find relevant the activities of the relevant CODATA National Committee.

⁷⁹ See Garavelli, Märkälä, & Liinamaa (2021)

⁸⁰ See Beckmann et al. (2021)

⁸¹ <https://www.openaire.eu/contact-noads> (accessed: 30.5.2023)

⁸² <https://codata.org/membership/national-members/> (accessed: 30.5.2023)

3.4.1.3 WorldFAIR case studies

Another useful source of cutting-edge data-related activity is happening in the cohort of case studies of the WorldFAIR project. This has been described in section 3.3.8 above, including the countries collaborating within each case study work package. These work packages are primarily considering the challenges of cross-domain research data interoperability and so will be excellent colleagues for prospective RDA working groups interested in that issue, as well as relevant to anyone seeking an overview of current data-related activity in the named countries.

3.4.1.4 Research Software Engineers (RSE) national/multinational associations

Research Software Engineers are people who combine professional software expertise with an understanding of research. They go by various job titles but the term Research Software Engineer (RSE) is fast gaining international recognition. The National/Multinational (RSE) Associations represents the RSE communities from specific countries, including: Belgium, Germany, Netherlands, United Kingdom, Australia and New Zealand, United States and Denmark. The International Council of RSE Associations was created as a forum to communicate between associations and to provide a platform for open discussion around international issues and affairs.

3.4.2 Regional approaches

Another approach of value to the Landscape Service is to consider regional activities and initiatives.

3.4.2.1 RDA regions

In the RDA, regions are expected to run activities to support growth in RDA membership and adoption of outputs in the local area. It is worth mentioning the two formal regional offices of RDA:

- RDA AISBL (the RDA TIGER Coordinator) previously developed as a set of European projects, is now formalised as a legal entity⁸³ and part of its developing strategy is to work in the European data sharing landscape and provide links to international activities in RDA. The most relevant outputs for this landscaping analysis are via RDA's work in EOSC Future (mentioned above in section 3.3.4) and involvement with the EOSC Future Open Calls programme.
- RDA US⁸⁴ which is funded by a range of USA-based funders and represents over 25% of the RDA global membership. RDA US provides a number of outputs e.g. webinars, podcasts that are relevant to the Landscape Analysis Service.

The RDA regions are supported by the RDA Regional Assembly body, which convenes once a month, and has over 29 countries represented. This is a formal body which provides a regional perspective on the work of the RDA. Here information is exchanged around the experience of building communities,

⁸³ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/rda-europe> (accessed: 30.5.2023)

⁸⁴ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/about-rda-us> (accessed: 30.5.2023)

running events, promoting standards, and having effective communication channels. There is also an RDA Coordination Group for the Regions⁸⁵ which is self-organised and has a multinational membership, and the landscape can benefit from any updates from this international group.

The following regions are represented in RDA:

- RDA Americas: <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/rda-americas>. This has been historically a long-standing region in the global RDA landscape. It is wider than the US and fosters collaboration between Canada and Costa Rica and Latin America.
- RDA in South-eastern Europe: <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/rda-south-eastern-europe>
- RDA Asia <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/rda-asia>

While it should be noted that the above groups don't produce outputs per se, RDA TIGER should attend the Regional Assembly meetings. This provides a good vehicle for updates on a technical level, for adoption and also to gather a picture on translations of outputs to other languages apart from English. The Regional Advisory Board oversees the Regional Assembly as a separate body⁸⁶.

3.4.2.2 Other regional initiatives and networks

It is important to keep an eye on the many diverse global networks, not all of which necessarily have a targeted focus on Open Science, data sharing or e-Infrastructures, but focus rather on supporting higher education and research in different ways. As a result, part of these activities might cover data-sharing challenges and might have corresponding outputs. The team identified a limited number of initiatives, but this is not an exhaustive list. There are also global NGOs (for example the START⁸⁷ network that has a focus on digital support activities in scientific disciplines in Africa and Asia) and the Landscape Analysis Service should keep mindful of this type of stakeholder.

Latin America

LA Referencia is a key player supporting a network of twelve national nodes representing countries in the Spanish-speaking world⁸⁸. They promote and share standards in the field of repository infrastructures and technologies, working together for common standards and repository guidelines. Many of these guidelines aim to align internationally, and they should be considered an important resource.

Australasia/Oceania

⁸⁵ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/rda-regions> (accessed: 30.5.2023)

⁸⁶ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/about-rda/organisational-bodies/rda-regional-advisory-board> (accessed: 30.5.2023)

⁸⁷ <https://start.org/our-work/> (accessed: 30.5.2023)

⁸⁸ <https://www.lareferencia.info/en/nodes> (accessed: 30.5.2023)

The most active regional network in Australasia is the Aero: the Australasian eResearch Organisations⁸⁹ which provides an advocacy forum with fourteen members from across the region to discuss and engage members on eResearch issues. It maintains a number of useful resources in data management but also topical issues such as high-performance computing (HPC). The site contains links to tools and resources. It links mainly to members' outputs, but it is worth the Landscape Service keeping an eye as it collates regional resources. AeRO also hosts a large eResearch conference every year⁹⁰.

Africa

There are significant pan- / regional African research projects and infrastructures and it is an active continent in terms of infrastructures and data sharing. Below is a list of initiatives that are likely to be relevant to our ongoing work.

The Africa Open Science Platform (AOSP)⁹¹ is emerging as a coordinating body for Open Science practices in the African region. It is a good resource for identifying regional activities and has a strong tie to other global activities, including a useful landscape report, as mentioned in section 3.1, which includes a Landscape analyses and includes its own strategy⁹². AOSP is the process of setting up regional nodes oriented towards aspects of this strategy. There have been national efforts to embrace Open Science through policies (Ethiopia) and national open science clouds such as SAOSC⁹³. The work is also being supported by data intensive research networks, for example DIRISA⁹⁴.

The Association of African Universities (AAU)⁹⁵ tackles strengthening capacity in higher education and acts as a representative organisation for universities. The AAU is involved in a number of relevant regional infrastructure projects the outcomes of which are interesting from a policy and a technical level⁹⁶.

There are many highly active research consortia and networks on the African continent that have long-standing engagement in data sharing and collaborative research practices, for RUFORUM⁹⁷ and H3BioNet⁹⁸. Africa Connect projects are 'accelerators' of National Research and Educational Network (NREN)s⁹⁹ in Africa. As well as providing technology infrastructure, NRENs also provide support for vital regional research projects. It is important to note that there are also African regional NREN alliances:

⁸⁹ <https://aero.edu.au/> (accessed: 30.5.2023)

⁹⁰ <https://conference.eresearch.edu.au/> (accessed: 30.5.2023)

⁹¹ <https://aosp.org.za/> (accessed: 30.5.2023)

⁹² <https://zenodo.org/record/2222418#.ZHmH1y8RpbU> (accessed: 30.5.2023)

⁹³ <https://www.egi.eu/project/sa-eu-dialogue-saosc/> (accessed: 23.6.2023)

⁹⁴ <https://www.dirisa.ac.za/>

⁹⁵ <https://aau.org/current-projects/afren/> (accessed: 30.5.2023)

⁹⁶ For example see: <https://aau.org/mapping-research-infrastructure-to-enhance-the-resilience-of-science-systems-in-sub-saharan-africa/> (accessed: 30.5.2023)

⁹⁷ <http://www.ruforum.org/> (accessed 22.6.2023)

⁹⁸ <https://www.h3abionet.org/> (accessed: 22.6.2023)

⁹⁹ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/National_research_and_education_network (accessed: 30.5.2023)

WACREN (West Africa)¹⁰⁰, UbuntuNet Alliance¹⁰¹ (Eastern and Southern Africa); ASREN (Arab States REN) for North Africa and the Arab states. A number of interesting data collection activities are taking place, often around disciplinary practices such as climate change and agriculture. Some domain-specific networks such as AfriGEOSS¹⁰² and GODAN Africa¹⁰³ deal with Africa-relevant research collection and data policies. As mentioned above, the WorldFAIR case studies are probably the most active in disciplinary data collection and interoperability and will provide the geographic and regional connections for example the Population Health and Agriculture Biodiversity case studies¹⁰⁴, both of which have partners in Kenya.

INSPIRE (The Implementation Network for Sharing Population Information from Research Entities)¹⁰⁵ is a multi-annual, multi-partner and multi-project initiative, coordinated by APHRC (the African Population and Health Research Centre, Nairobi, Kenya¹⁰⁶). GBIF (the Global Biodiversity Information Facility) is an international network and data infrastructure funded by the world's governments and aimed at providing anyone, anywhere, open access to data about all types of life on Earth.¹⁰⁷ At the time of writing, twenty African countries are members of the GBIF Africa regional node alongside five projects specialising in research areas within biodiversity science¹⁰⁸.

Asia

eResearch South East Asia¹⁰⁹ connects Australia and South East Asian researchers. However it produces little in terms of technical outputs although it lists some relevant landscaping reports on its site¹¹⁰.

CODATA has national committees representing China, India, Japan, Korea, Mongolia, and Taiwan, as discussed in section 3.4.1.2 above. In addition, there have been some activities related to the GOSC initiative (see section 3.2.7 above) in the region, including a recent regional Disaster Risk Reduction workshop in Thailand (which constitutes a GOSC Case Study) and some UNESCO / Association of Southeast Asian Nations (ASEAN) meetings on Open Science led by the Malaysian Open Science Cloud.

3.4.2.3 Regional approaches omitted

In the first stage, the RDA TIGER landscape analysis is based on immediately important initiatives, which have clearly identified potential to provide for important backgrounds for a number of RDA WGs. At this

¹⁰⁰ <https://wacren.net/en/> (accessed: 30.5.2023)

¹⁰¹ <https://ubuntunet.net/> (accessed: 30.5.2023)

¹⁰² https://www.earthobservations.org/me_201806_afrigeoss.php?t=home (accessed 22.6.2023)

¹⁰³ <https://www.godan.info/> (accessed 22.6.2023)

¹⁰⁴ <https://worldfair-project.eu/agricultural-biodiversity/> (accessed 22.6.2023)

¹⁰⁵ <https://aphrc.org/inspire/> (accessed 22.6.2023)

¹⁰⁶ <https://aphrc.org/> (accessed 22.6.2023)

¹⁰⁷ <https://www.gbif.org/composition/57twunvM3vrUotO12WDNgc/what-is-gbif> (accessed 22.6.2023)

¹⁰⁸ <https://www.gbif.org/the-gbif-network/africa> (accessed 22.6.2023)

¹⁰⁹ <https://www.ersea.org/> (accessed: 30.5.2023)

¹¹⁰ <https://www.ersea.org/eResearch%20South%20East%20Asia%202021%20Review.pdf> (accessed: 30.5.2023)

stage, this selection has not included policy tools such as the EOSC observatory¹¹¹ as policy tools and national level intelligence is out of scope of the work of RDA WGs which are creating data-sharing solutions. The need for such analysis will be reviewed however in the second iteration of the landscape analysis deliverable.

4. Landscape analysis database: prioritisation and processes

The next step in the creation of the landscape analysis database is to encode (i.e. input the data via automatic or manual processes) to the database. As this is a resource-demanding process, WP3 needs to prioritise the data sources to be included in the database, and to input them in order which is the most useful for the RDA TIGER project stakeholders. As records overtime become outdated, it will be possible to filter by date so the most recent items can be found.

RDA TIGER WP3 is intended to provide a landscape analysis service for the supported RDA WGs, and the prioritisation should then follow from known or expected needs of the WGs. Additional considerations can be made on the resource needs of the data ingestion, as well as on the potential of outsourcing (e.g. from other related projects) the ingestion processes. For this phase, WP3 had agreed on the following general order of priority for the data source input (and potentially revision):

1. **Immediate identified needs of the supported WGs:** As the WGs are the main target of this database, their immediate needs should be considered first, and any identified data source which could have necessary landscape data for their purposes should be considered as the highest priority. However, this can be problematic in some cases, if the content which could support the WG is not immediately clear from the overall categorisation of the data sources. In other words, there might be a good data source for a supported WG, but it cannot be identified before actually analysing it (and at the same time, ingesting it to the database).
2. **Data sources which have general and well-characterised immediate impact on RDA WG formation:** This includes RDA Working Groups and their outputs (both disciplinary and general), and (with lesser priority) the data from Interest Groups and Communities of Practice.
3. **Data sources which are relatively easily available and ingestible, and are unique to RDA TIGER actions:** These include e.g. WorldFAIR activities, GORC database, and CODATA groups. These could also include information on current EOSC projects collected by the EOSC Focus project, if the data is made available to the RDA TIGER project.
4. **Data sources which require significant resources to ingest, and are unlikely to be ingested by outside parties:** These include e.g. national programmes or initiatives, and regional programmes, as well as reformatting and ingestion of older literary sources.
5. **Data sources which are likely to be included in the database by other collaborative parties:** This could include some of the EOSC related outputs, as well as outputs from other projects and landscape activities.

¹¹¹ See for example <https://eoscobservatory.eosc-portal.eu/home> (accessed: 30.5.2023)

Note that this prioritisation is intended for the work plan of the WP3 in RDA TIGER, not necessarily the order the data is actually ingested in the database (e.g., by outside parties).

5. Next steps and conclusion

5.1 Further structuring and analyses of activities in the landscape

The initial survey of the landscape has identified a broad portfolio of programmes, initiatives, services, activities, projects, and structures that contribute in one way or another to a defined set of objectives, and in most cases contribute also to the goals and objectives of Open Science (section 3).

This portfolio of activities (as a general term) often has an implicit structure (for example, EOSC itself has task forces, supporting projects, governance structures, service providers, and the like), and the objectives, regional scope, and domain focus, amongst other dimensions, can vary depending on the level of detail. In addition, the typical output expected from activities (recommendations, specifications, operational services, advice, examples and templates) and the maturity of these outputs (aligned with, for example, a maturity classification or technology readiness level) will also be useful dimensions to record.

It is already possible to integrate and link these activities into a knowledge base as envisaged in the approaches and methodologies described in section 2, but we recommend a specific task in the next iteration of the landscape survey to further analyse and structure the activities identified in the Open Science landscape as described in section 3, based on the above considerations.

It is clear that it is beyond the scope of this landscape analysis exercise to cover all areas. Therefore, the team has learned early on to prioritise with the aims of RDA TIGER in mind. Going forward, the team needs to consider and prioritise what is the most beneficial for the RDA WGs that we aim to support.

5.2 Next steps

The next approach to discuss in the future landscaping activities is that of engaging the community to contribute to a common knowledge base of Open Science activities¹¹². This could be done by initiating a crowdsourcing approach from the RDA, EOSC and wider communities. The more stakeholders who add to it, the richer the landscape knowledge, and its connectivities will benefit implementing Open Science practices. It will also be advisable and useful to include these outputs into the standardisation of RDA working group activities, as foreseen for RDA TIGER WP4.

It is also worth reflecting in WP3 on the first feedback from the RDA pilots, where the RDA TIGER Services are in the first stages of development. One initial observation is that a body of knowledge will

¹¹² This will practically be implemented as a knowledge graph resource, using the same infrastructure as the RDA Maintenance Facility. RDA TIGER deliverable D4.1 (DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.8058923) describes this aspect in detail.

be hugely useful. New initiatives pop up all the time, and we often rely on serendipitous identification of similar initiatives.

A further observation is that awareness of the landscape goes wider than the body of knowledge being built and relies on a very proactive and interactive team. For example, EOSC projects and infrastructures are a good resource, especially the legacy of EOSC projects where some standards have been initiated but could benefit from going through the RDA processes and WGs to be finalised and community recognised. Often this kind of knowledge comes to the Facilitation Service by word of mouth and constant communication with relevant stakeholders. It should therefore be embedded in the Communications Service of RDA TIGER to ensure channels are kept open to discuss and swap ideas and access to a clear programme of events e.g webinars related to EOSC, or RDA global events. The team should spread the work and ensure they are in touch with the Communications Service to see a calendar of events to attend and report back on.

5.3 Concluding remarks

The RDA TIGER Landscape Analysis Service is a completely new service platform provided for the RDA and the wider open science community. Based on the requests and needs of the existing RDA WGs, and other RDA bodies, this service will provide immensely valuable tools for the communities to find, connect and sometimes use the past and current developments globally.

This deliverable is the first step towards building this service, presenting the problem statement, the overall scope of the landscape analysis database, a plan for technical implementation, and a prioritised list of data sources to be included in the database. The document also presents the key next steps in the development, with the aim of creating a common community resource for RDA TIGER service provision, but also to the whole community. The service provision to the RDA TIGER supported groups will be the next major test case for this service, improving the overall concept and testing its feasibility in real life situations.

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Appendix A: RDA Maintenance Facility Structure

In the list below, it is possible to see the elements that have been identified as part of the work to build the RDA Maintenance Facility. These elements will be used in the RDA Maintenance Facility to tag and contextualise other elements. . The list is not comprehensive, and will be updated over time.

- Activities
 - Events
 - Workshops and Webinars
 - BoF Sessions
 - Plenaries
 - Initiatives
- Structures
 - Content- Focused Structures
 - Interest Groups
 - Working Groups
 - Coordination Groups
 - National Groups
 - Communities of Practice
 - Governance Structures and Organisational Bodies
 - RDA Council
 - RDA Council Subgroups
 - RDA Funders Forum
 - RDA Organisational Advisory Board
 - RDA Regional Advisory Board
 - RDA Technical Advisory Board
 - RDA Secretary General
 - RDA Secretariat
- Resources
 - RDA Endorsed Recommendations
 - RDA Supporting Outputs
- Stakeholders
 - Research Performing Organisations
 - Repositories
 - Researchers
 - Individuals (Members)
 - Institution

These lists are included into a graph-based data model that defines relations between the list elements, as and where applicable. Some examples:

1. The individual members of RDA have a relationship to Working Groups and Interest Groups as co-chairs, and individual members are usually (though not exclusively) the source of authors for RDA outputs - recommendations and supporting materials.
2. Working Groups, Interests Groups, or Individual Members may all be the originators of Birds-of-a-Feather events, and these events could in turn lead to the creation of new Working or Interest Groups.

There are many similar examples of these relationships between the entities in the list.

The Landscaping Service manages its knowledge base and enables a querying of the Facility via additional tag terms that adds a landscape perspective. Examples of these are the vocabulary under development to describe the elements, features, and attributes of data infrastructures in the GORC Working Group, lists of projects, initiatives, and structures provided by EOSC, and so on. This adds additional elements and relations to a graph-based vocabulary that can be used to classify and contextualise content.

The relationship between the RDA Maintenance Facility, the Landscape Analysis requirement, and supporting infrastructure is elaborated in full in deliverable D4.1.

Appendix B: Landscape analysis use cases

The Facilitation Service in RDA TIGER runs a service early on in the WG life-cycle to scan the existing landscape and identify similar activities on the topic. The following use cases were identified by the members of the work package to date in order to help guide the Facilitation Service to ask the right questions and to eventually to query the knowledge base with the right topics, people involved or existing pathways.

#	Group	Description
UC-01	RDA	Do any existing RDA WGs have [topic T] as part of their scope?
UC-02	RDA	Are there any RDA WGs with co-chairs from [institution I]?
UC-03	RDA	Are there any RDA WGs with co-chairs from [country C]?
UC-04	RDA	Are there any RDA WGs with co-chairs from [global region R]?
UC-05	RDA	Which WGs are connected with [pathway P]?
UC-06	RDA	Does the RDA have WGs relevant to [discipline area D]?
UC-07	RDA	What RDA members are connected to [topic T]/[discipline area D]/[institution I]/[country C]/[global region R]?
UC-08	EOSC	Are there current EOSC-developments in [global region R]?
UC-09	CODATA	How many CODATA National Committees are based in [global region R]?
UC-10	Various	Is there an [EOSC task force CODATA Task Group ReSA task force] on [topic T]?

